

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Identification of mental disorders among adolescents based on Global School-Based Student Health Survey (GSHS) in Kendari, Indonesia

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Abstract

According to Basic Health Research, the prevalence of mental health disorders in Indonesia increased to 9.8% in 2018. Meanwhile, in Southeast Sulawesi Province, the prevalence of mental disorders reached 11% with a total of 14,819 cases. The highest cases occurred in Kendari City, namely 2,249 people with a percentage of 12.17%. This study aimed to identify the mental health disorders among adolescents in Kendari City. A descriptive cross-sectional design was conducted in this study. The population was all students of Vocational School 1 in Kendari and the sample size was 49 respondents selected by accidental sampling. Data was collected through filled out questionnaires that adopted from Global School-Based Student Health Survey (GSHS) in 2021. Data analysis was carried out univariately using the epi info 7 application. The results of the study showed that majority of respondents (79.5%), 2% of respondents had attempted suicide. The implementation of stress management in schools was in the poor category (73.5%) and 89.8% of respondents have parents who play an active role in their lives. It was concluded that the majority of students experienced mental disorders and there was even students who have suicide attempt. Lack of implementation of stress management in schools. However, most of the respondents' parents contribute active in their lives. Therefore, it is necessary to implement stress management in schools regularly such as health education, counseling and Focus Group Discussions (FGD) involving all school officials, students and parents.

Keywords: Adolescent; Mental Disorder; Stress management; Suicide attempt; Parents' role

1. Introduction

Mental health is a state of mental well-being that allows a person to cope with the stresses of life, realize their abilities, study well and work well, and contribute to their community. Mental health is an integral component of health and well-being that underlies individual and collective abilities to make decisions, build relationships, and shape the world in which they live. Mental health also a fundamental human right that is essential for personal, community and socio-economic development(1). Mental health has an impact on a person's daily life or future, including children and adolescents. Maintaining and protecting children's mental health is an important aspect that can help children develop better in the future (2).

Mental health conditions include mental disorders and psychosocial disabilities as well as other mental conditions associated with significant distress, impaired functioning, or risk of self-harm. In 2019, 970 million people worldwide lived with a mental disorder, with anxiety and depression the most common. In 2020, the number of people living with anxiety disorders and depression increased significantly due to the COVID-19 pandemic (3). Meanwhile, in Indonesia itself, based on the results of Basic Health Research, it was revealed that the prevalence of sufferers of mental health disorders in Indonesia in 2013 was around 6%, then increased to 9.8% with emotional mental disorders in 2018 (4). The prevalence of cases of emotional mental disorders in Southeast Sulawesi Province reached 11% with a total of

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14,819 cases. Emotional mental disorders in the 15-24 year age group showed the highest rate compared to other age groups, namely with a total of 3,811 cases or around 10.28%, with the highest number of cases found in Kendari City, namely 2,249 people with a percentage of 12.17% (5).

Disturbed mental health conditions can cause difficulties in all aspects of life, including relationships with family, friends and society. Globally, mental disorders account for 1 in 6 years lived with disability. People with severe mental health conditions die 10 to 20 years earlier than the general population. Having a mental health disorder increases the risk of suicide and experiencing human rights violations (3).

Mental health problems often occur in childhood and early adolescence. Depression and anxiety are the largest causes of the burden of disease and disability experienced by adolescents. Teenagers are one of the groups at high risk of experiencing mental health problems or mental health disorders. The second growth occurs during adolescence, namely growth from childhood to the process of human maturity, namely adulthood. During adolescence, physical, biological and psychological changes occur. Adolescents must be able to adapt to these many changes, otherwise this can cause various mental health problems (6).

Based on the results of a national school-based health survey (Junior High School and High School) conducted by the Indonesian Ministry of Health which was published in 2015, it was stated that there are ten behavioral factors that pose a risk to adolescent health, one of which is disturbed mental and emotional health. In the three regions surveyed, namely Sumatra, Java and Bali, outside Java and Bali, the results showed that 46.01% of students experienced loneliness, 42.18% of students experienced excessive anxiety or worry, 62.38% of students experienced emotional disorders, namely loneliness, excessive worry and even suicidal thoughts (7).

Stress is one of the mental disorders causes in teenagers. Stress that can affect mental health is more common in teenagers who experience emotional stress, academic pressure, family problems, or conflicts with friends. Excessive stress can be a major risk factor causing suicidal thoughts in adolescents. Parents can help teenagers deal with this stress. Teenagers can manage stress better if they receive support and positive communication from their parents (8).

Vocational School 1 Kendari is a state vocational high school with a focus on business and management careers which is located near the city center. This school is one of the most popular schools with very tight competition in both academic and non-academic fields(9). Students at this school are expected to have superior skills in their respective fields. If students are unable to undergo the adjustment process both psychologically and environmentally at school, it will certainly be a stress factor for them. Based on the problems above, researchers were interested in conducting research on "Identification of Mental Disorders Among Adolescents in Kendari, Indonesia".

2. Material and methods

A cross sectional descriptive study was conducted in this study to identify the mental disorders among adolescents in Kendari. The study was carried out in May 2024 at Vocational School 1 Kendari. The population were all students of Vocational School 1 Kendari with a total sample of 49 respondents that taken by accidental sampling technique. The data collected through filled out the questionnaires that was adopted from Global School-Based Student Health Survey (GSHS) questionnaire developed by WHO in 2021. The GSHS questionnaire consists of 10 different modules ranging from health behavior, protective factors (role of parents), and demographics. This study measured mental health disorders (5 questions), suicide attempts (2 questions), protective factors or the role of parents (12 questions) and stress management classes at school (5 questions). The data was processed and analyzed univariately using the epi info 7 application.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Characteristic of Respondents

The following is a table of characteristics of respondents in this study:

Table 1 showed the distribution of respondents based on the sex, out of 49 respondents the majority were female, 29 respondents (59.2%) and the remaining 20 respondents were male (40.8%). Meanwhile, the characteristics of respondents according to age, the most respondents were 16 years old with 32 respondents (65.3%) and the fewest were 18 years old with 2 respondents (4.1%). Based on grade, out of the 49 respondents, the most respondents came from grade X, namely 30 respondents (61.2%) and the fewest were grade XI namely 19 respondents (37.8)

Table 1 Characteristics of Respondents at Vocational School 1 Kendari

Characteristics	Frequency (n= 49)	Percentage (%)
Sex		
Male	20	40.8
Female	29	59.2
Age (Years Old)		
15	6	40.8
16	32	65.3
17	9	18.4
18	2	4.1
Grade		
X	30	61.2
XI	19	37.8

Source: Primary Data (May, 2024)

3.2 Mental Disorder Identification

Mental health is a state of mental well-being that enables a person to cope with the stresses of life, realize their abilities, study well and work well, and contribute to their community (1). Meanwhile, mental disorders according to WHO (WHO, 2022a) are conditions characterized by clinically significant disturbances in a person's cognition, emotional regulation or behavior. It is usually associated with distress or impairment in important areas of functioning (3).

Table 2 Identification of Mental Health Disorder Among Adolescents in Kendari

Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Mental Health Disorder		
Experiencing Mental Disorders	39	79.6
Not Experiencing Mental Disorders	10	20.4
Suicide Attempt		
Once	1	2.0
Never	48	98.0
Stress Management in Schools		
Good	13	26.5
Poor	36	73.5
The role of parents		
Active	44	89.8
Non active	5	10.2

Source: Primary Data (May, 2024)

Based on table 2 above, out of 49 respondents, the majority of respondents experienced mental disorders as many as 39 respondents (79.6%) and a small percentage did not experience mental disorders as many as 10 respondents (20.4%). The suicide attempt variable showed that the majority of respondents have never attempted suicide, namely 48 respondents (98.0%), but 1 respondent (2.0%) has attempted suicide. Based on the stress management variable held at school, it showed that the majority of respondents stated that the stress management carried out at school was in the poor category, namely 36 respondents (73.5%), while the remaining 13 respondents were in the good category (26.5%). The distribution of respondents based on parental role showed that the majority of respondents' parents were active in playing a role on their children's mental health, namely 44 respondents (89.8%), while those who do not active were 5 respondents (10.2%).

3.2.1. *Mental Disorder*

Karl Menninger said that mental health individuals are those who have the ability to restrain themselves, show intelligence, behave with consideration for other people's feelings, and have a happy attitude to life. Mental health is an important part of health. A healthy mental condition will enable individuals to realize their abilities, be able to overcome stress and problems in life, be productive at work and contribute to the community (10).

In table 2, the results of research on mental health disorders showed that the majority of respondents (79.6%) experienced mental disorders. The mental disorders experienced in this study included anxiety disorders, feelings of sadness, depression or hopelessness, not focusing at school and doing negative things in the face of these disorders. Emotional mental disorders and depression in adolescents is a necessary condition gets serious attention because it can influence behavior, emotions, and ways of thinking teenager (11).

Adolescence is a vulnerable age for experiencing mental health problems. Mental health problems that occur in teenagers can be caused by various factors. Biological, psychological and social changes can be risk factors or protective factors for the emergence of mental health problems in adolescents. Therefore, detection of mental health problems is very important, so that efforts can be made as early as possible to prevent the emergence of mental health problems which can impact the quality of life of teenagers (12).

The results of this study are in line with research which states that the majority of teenagers (65.5%) have poor levels of mental health (13). Adolescence is an important period for developing social and emotional habits that are important for mental well-being. This includes adopting healthy sleep patterns; exercise regularly; develop coping, problem-solving, and interpersonal skills; and learn to manage emotions. A protective and supportive environment in the family, at school and in the wider community is important. Various factors influence mental health. The more risk factors a teenager face, the greater the potential impact on their mental health. Factors that may contribute to stress during adolescence include exposure to adversity, pressure to conform to peers, and identity exploration (14).

3.2.2. *Suicide Attempt*

Bridge, et al argue that suicidal ideation refers to thoughts about hurting or killing oneself (15). Meanwhile, according to the American Psychiatric Association (APA), suicidal behavior on its official website defines suicidal behavior as a form of action by an individual by killing themselves and most often occurs due to depression or other mental illness (16). This study founded that the majority of respondents had never attempted suicide. However, 2% of respondent had attempted suicide. This needs to be given very serious attention because attempting suicide is the initial stage of suicide. This research is in line with research which stated that there were 0.9% of respondents who have thought about and planned suicide, causing them to experience psychological disorders such as fear of the social environment due to experiencing bullying and often thinking about ending their life but too scared to do it (17).

Based on previous research stated that suicide can be caused by several factors. Among the problems faced by people who intend to commit suicide, namely: 1) Depression. The depression they experience is the culmination of all feelings of guilt, anger, meaninglessness and undesirability. Severe depression is one of the causes of suicide. 2) Self-concept. Many people experience self-concept problems, especially teenagers. A false self-concept makes them feel that their presence is unwanted, worthless and that no one loves them. This wrong self-concept is also influenced by the environment, especially close friends. Someone tries to be what their close friends want them to be so that they can be accepted and recognized by their group. 3) Relationships within the family. Family relationships involve parental divorce and parental acceptance. Parental divorce hurts family members, especially teenage children, and makes them feel unloved and blame themselves for the divorce. Parents who do not accept their teenage children as themselves, make teenagers try to be someone else and feel that their parents will only love them when they become the teenagers their parents want them to be (18).

The high prevalence of suicidal ideation in adolescents can occur due to differences in the development of the adolescent brain. Giedd said that the part of a teenager's limbic system which is responsible for emotions, motivation and motivation begins to mature at the age of 15 years. This makes teenagers have great curiosity and the courage to do risky things. On the other hand, the part of the brain called the prefrontal cortex which is responsible for cognitive function does not fully mature until the age of 25 years. This makes teenagers more vulnerable to carrying out risky actions without contemplating. These risky things include suicidal behavior. Suicide is also inseparable from the interaction of four factors, namely biological, psychological, cognitive and environmental (19).

3.2.3. *Stress Management in Schools*

Stress is a condition that arises from the interaction between humans and work and is characterized by changes in humans that force them to deviate from their normal functions. Stress is a form of psychological reaction that normally occurs when the burden of life increases, one of which is the burden of work. In overcoming this stress, stress management is needed which aims to improve the quality of life for the better (20). The research results showed that the majority of respondents stated that the stress management carried out by the school was in the poor category. Stress management in question is the role of schools in teaching stress management to students, including how to regulate emotions, signs of depression and suicidal behavior, stress management and what to do when a friend is thinking about committing suicide.

Stress management is the process of overcoming or finding a way out to resolve, cure the pressures that exist in oneself such as stress. The relationship between coping with stress and mental health is that it can help individuals in the process of recovering from the stressful experiences they have felt. So that their mental health improves, they can easily think clearly and have a healthy and normal mentality. Coping or stress management skills are very necessary for every individual. In order to have an ideal and healthy mentality, the ability to think positively must be developed (21).

Based on previous research, good stress management and emotional management skills can increase self-adaptation to problems and demands that arise, as well as being able to assess, understand emotions objectively and express them. Good emotional management can also guide the thinking process, deepen knowledge about things that cause anxiety, and support emotional and intellectual growth. Experts explain that managing a student's emotions is very necessary in creating high individual performance and abilities. A student who is able to understand, differentiate and use emotions or feelings well knows how to stay motivated even though he is in a stressful condition (22).

According to Sahni and Kumar in (20), stress is one of the problems that occurs in schools apart from conflict. Stress usually occurs, among other things, because the burden is too heavy and the problems are very serious. Loads that are too heavy tend to cause a person to become frustrated and stressed, because they are considered beyond their ability to bear. In dealing with conflict and stress, a school principal has a very big role. What needs to be done is to diagnose the conditions that are occurring at that time, then take action through communications. A leader in a school actually has the task of solving problems that occur in his school (23).

3.2.4. *The Role of Parents*

One of the factors that plays a role in the emotional mental development of teenagers is the family. The family provides the basis for forming a child's personality, behavior, character, morals and education. Factors that influence teenagers' mental and emotional emotions in the family environment are parenting patterns, family conditions, morals in the family, and relationships with siblings. Factors in the family that have an important role in creating a prosperous family and preventing mental and emotional problems are the application of parenting patterns (7).

The research results showed that the majority of respondents have parents who play an active role in their lives. Emotional closeness and attention from parents play a positive role in mental health. Family is the first and main place for children to grow and develop. Family relationships show a positive relationship with suicidal ideation. This relationship indicates that family relationships are an important protective factor in the emergence of suicidal ideation in adolescents. Good family relationships, including with parents, make the tendency to have suicidal ideation in teenagers lower. In general, it was found that the complexity of interactions between family, social and emotional factors trigger suicidal thoughts (24).

This research were in line with research which stated that the majority of teenagers (56%) play a role in their lives. 72% of respondents stated that they often received advice from their parents, which was supported by 62% or 32 people stating that their parents rarely ignored students when they needed it. Apart from that, parents also often provide attention, show affection and have open communication. Parental support and freedom/not restraining children are protective factors for parents against mental disorders that may be experienced by teenagers (25). Based on research, the role of parents in children's mental health is very important, especially when it concerns inner child problems, because the child's condition is still in the process of growth and development, but there are still many parents who ignore this and lack awareness of the inner child. children, especially teenagers aged 15-24 years. Apart from that, there is a lack of educational media to help parents understand the inner child. If this is left unchecked, many children will be negatively impacted by the inner child, so a visual educational media design is needed for parents to increase understanding and awareness about the inner child, especially for teenagers aged 15-24 years (26).

4. Conclusion

Based on this research, it can be concluded that the majority of respondents experience mental health disorders. In the aspect of attempting suicide, most respondents have never attempted suicide, but there was still respondent who has. The implementation of stress management in schools is considered to be lacking. However, most parents play an active role in their children's lives so they have good interaction and attachment. This can have a positive effect on mental health. Thus, it is hoped that the school will strengthen the mental health program, by holding stress management classes regularly such as health education, providing easy access to counseling, conducting Focus Group Discussions (FGD) at school involving all school officials and parents of students.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants in this study.

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